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PREDICTION OF THE FUTURE: NEW ROLES OF THE UNIVERSITY LIBRARIAN

Objective. The article analyzes the new roles of librarians - facilitator, tutor, moderator, presents their introduction into the activities of the university library, reveals the impact of innovations on the effectiveness of the library and the university. **Methods.** The study was conducted by reviewing publications related to clarifying the new roles of librarians in the practice of modern university libraries, summarizing the experience of the Scientific Library of Kharkiv Petro Vasylenko National Technical University of Agriculture (SL KhNTUA) to introduce new activities. **Results.** During the study, the authors determined that the SL KhNTUA' introduction of the innovative forms in terms of new roles of librarians (facilitator, tutor, moderator) contributes to the development and diversification of library services, increase in the role of SL as an active partner of the university in research, teaching and educational work; emphasizes and strengthens the role of the library in raising the ranking of the university. **Conclusions.** *The originality of the work* is to expand ideas about the new roles of librarians in the activities of the university library, which is an important factor in assessing the effectiveness of its management. *Practical value.* The obtained results are used to improve the management of human resources of university libraries.

Keywords: library; library facilitator; librarian tutor; moderation in the library; human resources management

Introduction

The development of a new digital society in the field of science and education requires new information support, which should be provided to the library in the activities of universities. Other functions related to publishing processes, digital and licensing resources, creation of digital content of own generation, presence of social media, etc. are added to traditional library activity. All this encourages librarians to master new roles that were previously uncharacteristic of them. Librarians are gradually losing their primary responsibilities of traditional reference work and collection management, while new functions related to research support, data management, bibliometrics, digital initiatives, scientific communication and user experience are increasingly becoming a part of the university librarian's activities.

Information-analytical monitoring and bibliometric analysis for many libraries is gradually becoming one of the main areas of work (Kostyrko & Korolova, 2020), and due to the introduction of the Library Publishing model, the influence and importance of the academic library as the main subject of scientific publications, formation of higher education institutions brand and the growth of the authority of Ukrainian science in general increase (Kolesnykova & Matveyeva, 2019).

In our opinion, today librarians should combine the competencies of a librarian-teacher, librarian-curator, tutor, facilitator, coach, moderator, which will ensure the effective use of the benefits of information technology, resources and services. This aspect of the librarian's activity in the information and educational trajectory of higher education institutions at the present stage is not considered properly by researchers of library work. The aim is to analyze the activity of a

modern librarian of a higher education institution as an agent of change and to trace how in the conditions of digitalization such new functions and roles of librarians as library tutoring, moderation, facilitation are adapted to the needs of users on the example of the work of the Scientific Library of Kharkiv Petro Vasylenko National Technical University of Agriculture (SL KhNTUA).

Results and Discussion

The transformation of the national education system has created the preconditions for the establishment of a new State Biotechnology University (SBTU) in Kharkiv to meet the needs of the labor market in relevant specialists and improve the competitiveness of obtaining quality higher education. As an institution of higher education, SBTU already has historical origins, names and places, because its creation is based on long-term achievements of four Kharkiv institutions of higher education – Kharkiv Petro Vasylenko National Technical University of Agriculture, Kharkiv National Agrarian University named after V.V. Dokuchaiev, Kharkiv State Zooveterinary Academy and Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade and their libraries.

The peculiarity of the Scientific Library (SL) of SBTU as a new structural unit of the newly created regional university is that it not only combines documentary and electronic resources of book collections of four universities, but also has a chance to secure a leading position among libraries of higher education through the best practices of a work of each of the libraries that are part of the current SL.

It is currently proposed to review the practical experience of the SL of KhNTUA on human resources management in the global trend of digitalization of society, to clarify the new roles of librarians as navigators and consultants in the digital educational environment. Accordingly, the functional view of the role of management in the management system of a modern library is changing. The successful operation of libraries in the face of external and internal challenges is a competitive, complementary team in which the leader must combine such management styles as producer of results, administrator, entrepreneur and integrator (Nikolaienko, 2019, 2020). Such management styles, in our opinion, will help library managers to create a complementary team, in which each of the management styles must be complemented by five main functions of the manager: decision-making, implementation, team building, personnel management, change management, and behavior and communication. New challenges in society require flexibility from library managers at all levels, as well as from librarians who already combine the skills of librarian-teacher, librarian-curator, tutor, facilitator, coach, moderator. In the era of digital technology, new roles of librarians can consciously keep up with the times, ensure the development of their personal functions (activity, sociability, dynamism, efficiency, tolerance, competence, creativity) encourage self-improvement and self-organization. Recently, the functions of librarian, moderator, librarian-facilitator became popular in the National Library of KhNTUA, which was emphasized during the II Scientific-Practical Conference "Library and Information Environment as a Driver of Change and Innovation in Education", dedicated to the 90th anniversary of the book collection.

Library tutoring in the library service of KhNTUA has found its proper place in the process of self-education of users. Unlike the traditional "informing" and "information literacy education" that has always been and remains an important function of the library, tutoring has become a reliable mentoring tool in helping users adapt to the information world. Library tutoring is the responsibility and personal contribution of the librarian to the development of the users, to their success, and, hence, to the success of the university. Practice proves that no matter

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how independent the user is, there are situations in which a person needs support from a certain specialist. Currently, such support is needed by scientific and pedagogical staff of universities of different age categories. Among them are young people with a high level of computer literacy, and older people who are not well aware of new information technologies. These categories of users need support from librarians-tutors, because many new concepts recently entered the life of each of them. They include databases of scientific information, scientometrics, bibliometrics, citation index, Hirsch index, impact factor, journal quartile, bibliographic managers (EndNote, Mendeley), publication styles (MLA, APA, Harvard, etc.), References, identifiers and various author profiles, etc.

Performing professional tasks as a librarian tutor, the library specialists ensure the implementation of three functions: consultant (information and information support), mentor (providing advice, establishing an algorithm of actions), facilitator (establishing and maintaining information links and interaction between participants in the educational process, adaptation of users to new forms of scientific communication (Rybalchenko, 2020).

Thanks to the persistence and responsible attitude to the innovative changes of the library staff, we have positive results of the evaluation of the library in this direction among the scientific and pedagogical staff and the administration. According to the faculty and management of the university, this approach to user needs has had positive results and to some extent affected the performance of the university, in particular, in such rankings as Scopus Rating of Ukrainian universities and International ranking of universities in the Webometrics World Ranking Web of Universities). Thus, according to the ranking of Ukrainian universities according to Scopus, the university got 118th place in 2018, 72 – in 2021. According to the indicators of work in the International ranking of world universities Ranking Web of Universities (Webometrics) had in 2018 –107, 2021– 76th place. In addition, according to the results of the survey "On the quality of structural units of the university", which took place in the second semester of 2020/2021 year in KhNTUA, SL took 2nd place among 21 subsections of the institution.

Undoubtedly, this is entirely the merit of the scientific and pedagogical workers themselves, who publish the results of their scientific activity, choosing for publication the best scientific periodicals included in the DB Scopus and WoS.

But the library, carrying out analytical support of scientific and publishing activities of the university, systematically conducts painstaking tutoring with users as an individual educational practice, where, communicating individually, he/she explains the importance of scientometric indicators, h-index, opportunities to increase publication activity and citations increase, searches for scientific publications to publish research results, obtains analytical reports, and monitors the profile of the scientist and the university. By tracking the profiles of scientists in Google Scholar in order to display them in the information-analytical system "Bibliometrics of Ukrainian Science", librarian tutors not only provide advisory and practical assistance in creating profiles of scientists in this database (DB), but also improve user skills in editing and ensuring the completeness and accuracy of the reflection of scientific achievements. The work contributed to the improvement of TRANSPARENCY (or OPENNESS) in the Webometrics ranking and provided the overall best position of the university in it.

The introduction of a new role of librarian in the information and educational space of the university in the Scientific Library of KhNTUA, related to the use of moderator functions, contributed to the creation of high-quality electronic information content of higher education institutions. In the SL of KhNTUA the functions of moderator were introduced in two areas of work: monitoring the filling of the electronic archive "Open Archive KhNTUA" and participation in the organization of publishing activities of departments. When working with documents for publication in the repository, the librarian-moderator checks the compliance of the

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posted content to the selected collection, the correctness of fields and subfields in accordance with the adopted instructions and compliance of the attached bibliographic record in accordance with SBTU GOST 7.1: 2006 "System of standards for information, library and publishing cases. Bibliographic record. Bibliographic description. General requirements and rules of compilation".

The main aspects of the work of the library moderator of educational and educational-methodical content is participation in the preparation of the "Plan of publishing activities of the university departments for the academic year" for sound decision-making on the issues of book supply of primary disciplines, providing access to e-versions of scientific, educational and educational-methodical publications through the electronic catalog of the SL. In addition, for the design and preparation of printed university products the library has prepared and issued guidelines for teachers "General requirements for the design of scientific, educational and teaching publications, 2019", developed on the basis of legislation of Ukraine on publishing, regulations of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, state standards of Ukraine, other normative documents (Martynenko & Bocharova, 2020).

A strong impetus to positive changes in the renewal of meaningful library communication with users was provided by the introduction of pedagogical facilitation in the practice of the SL. As a process, it is the facilitation and at the same time strengthening the productivity of education and training, the development of participants in the pedagogical process due to their communication style and personality traits of the teacher and student. This is the recognition of the student as the main figure of the whole educational process. The main tasks of facilitation provide an understanding that the professional qualities of librarians are gaining new meaning, the range of tasks they are involved in, is expanding. In our opinion, the activities in the library environment that take place using facilitation methods are aimed at meeting the information and knowledge needs of all categories of users and all participants have the opportunity to discuss problems, provide recommendations, show emotions, and learn together. Facilitation methods can work as a separate form of group work, and they can also be part of an event. SL staff conducts practical "Electronic resources of the Scientific Library: search and use" with elements of the classic "Brainstorming", one of the most common methods of facilitation, which helps to formulate as many ideas as possible on a given question in a very limited period of time. Brainstorming, as a method, involves everyone in the discussion, reveals new, unusual ideas, creates many options, stimulates synergies in the group, prevents premature evaluation of ideas. Discussions, debates, reading conferences, round tables and other dialogue forms of cultural and educational work now require facilitation – special actions that encourage students to be not passive listeners, but the most active participants. In facilitation, the focus shifts to the group, the main thing is the group, participants, and those who work, their thoughts, ideas, not the opinion of a librarian! To conduct an hour of communication "Space of Tolerance – Space of Coexistence", the method of "round methodology" was chosen, which is valuable because it unites a group of people. Dialogue forms of cultural and educational work, the living word of the librarian give a powerful impetus to the development of all areas of the reader's personality, personal development and creative potential of the librarian. During the event, thanks to the method of facilitation "Round Method", the actions of librarians brought the Scientific Library closer to students, coincided with the desire of participants to receive information and communicate in an unusual for them emotionally rich, lively, dynamic form. In the practice of the National Library, there is experience in implementing the elements of "World cafe" – a method for developing ideas and activating cognitive activity in the process of discussing the selected topic. The main idea of the "World Café" is to make sure that participants know the solution to the problem better than they think. Only in the course of trusting style of communication and cooperation, new knowledge can be discovered. Facilitation is used in

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relation to offline communication, but the current state of pedagogical science and facilitation methods effectively adapt it to the online environment. The game is an interesting and promising type of activity, which is provided by one of the facilitation methods used by the library staff with the university department to create a webquest "Ukrainian (Cossack) Baroque". Leading librarian of the SL Perevoznik T.I. and Professor of Culture, Sports and Tourism Department Grabar N.G., creating this webquest to develop problems in the discipline "History of Ukrainian Culture", used the game elements, a great tool for research and study of this topic. The webquest "Ukrainian (Cossack) Baroque" was tested in classes on the history of Ukrainian culture and received positive feedback from both students and teachers of the department (Bezdolna, 2020).

Employees of the SL KhNTUA actively use community management to create a community loyal to the library: we find and unite active users around the library to jointly solve existing problems, make users full participants in the educational process.

To create a community in the library: the target audience is studied, university staff, faculty, scientists and students; a loyal core is formed, opinion leaders are identified, through which active users are involved, communication and cooperation with institutes and departments is maintained. Currently, we can talk about the library department community with the Department of Culture, Sports and Tourism of the Educational and Scientific Institute of Business and Management. The web-quest "Ukrainian Cossack Baroque" created jointly in 2019 has been successfully tested and used in the educational process. In the nearest future we plan to join the community of the UNESCO Department "Philosophy of Human Communication" and socio-humanitarian disciplines to develop an interactive poster "Literary Kharkiv: tourist diversity" and work with the Department of Marketing and Media Communications to present publications within the project "Library of Marketing Specialist" in online format. The scientific library can offer departments assistance in mastering online services, trainings on creating web quests, virtual tours, interactive posters, etc. (Perevoznik, 2020).

Conclusions

Nothing stands still, everything changes, this is the law of life and those who look only to the past or only to the present will undoubtedly miss the future (John Fitzgerald Kennedy).

Against the background of general civilizational changes, the Scientific Library of KhNTUA as an information and cultural-educational institution has undergone a significant transformation, and it is constantly changing to be irreplaceable. Librarians rethink their roles, guided by the transition from the printed past to the future on the Internet, review their products and services, refocusing on their customers. Based on the main functions of the library and taking into account the requirements of the time, the library of the institution provides access to information for educational, scientific, cultural needs in any format, and in any way, using pedagogical methods, expands the range of information and management technologies, tries to demonstrate its importance to the largest possible audience and open access not only to available resources, but also to orient the user in the many information flows of today, combining traditional functions of identification, search and evaluation of information with more conceptual concepts of requesting, analyzing and using information. Information skills are now closely connected with technological and pedagogical skills and are naturally combined in the work with the competencies of librarian-teacher, librarian-curator, tutor, facilitator, coach, moderator, which provides effective use of the benefits of information technology, resources, services. Possession of such skills is important in our opinion, not only for working with library clients, but also in the library staff.

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ПЕРЕДБАЧЕННЯ МАЙБУТНЬОГО: НОВІ РОЛІ УНІВЕРСИТЕТСЬКОГО БІБЛІОТЕКАРЯ

Мета. В статті проаналізовано нові ролі бібліотекарів – фасилітатор, тьютор, модератор,

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представлено їх запровадження у діяльність університетської бібліотеки, виявлено вплив нововведень на результативність діяльності бібліотеки і університету. **Методика:** дослідження проводилось шляхом огляду публікацій, пов'язаних із з'ясуванням нових ролей бібліотекарів в практиці роботи сучасних університетських бібліотек, узагальнення досвіду Наукової бібліотеки Харківського національного технічного університету сільського господарства імені Петра Василенка (НБ ХНТУСГ) по запровадженню в роботу нових видів діяльності. **Результати.** Під час дослідження авторами визначено, що впровадження НБ ХНТУСГ у діяльність інноваційних форм у вигляді нових ролей бібліотекарів (фасилітатор, тьютор, модератор) сприяє розвитку та урізноманітненню бібліотечного сервісу, зростанню ролі НБ як активного партнера університету у дослідженнях, навчанні і виховній роботі; підкреслює та зміцнює роль бібліотеки у підвищенні рейтингових показників університету. **Висновки.** *Наукова новизна* полягає в розширенні уявлень про нові ролі бібліотекарів в діяльності університетської бібліотеки, що є важливим чинником для оцінювання результативності її управлінської діяльності. *Практична значимість.* Отримані результати використовуються для удосконалення управління кадровим потенціалом університетських бібліотек.

Ключові слова: бібліотека; бібліотечний фасилітатор; бібліотьютор; модераторство в бібліотеці; управління кадровим потенціалом

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